

2025

opencitations.net

OpenCitations

Annual Report

Prepared by

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with the advice from the International Advisory Board for OpenCitations

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2025 at a glance

Silvio Peroni

OpenCitations Director

As I do every year, I am here to set the stage for 2026 by recalling the achievements of the past year. OpenCitations has undergone a significant phase of growth and transformation, particularly in how we communicate and interact with our community. We have renewed our visual identity and redesigned our website to make our services more accessible, transparent, and easier to navigate for researchers, librarians, publishers, and all those who (do and will) rely on open scholarly metadata in their daily work.

At the same time, we have continued strengthening the infrastructure itself: expanding our datasets, improving interoperability, refining our governance model, and investing in long-term sustainability. Yet, if there is one lesson that has become increasingly clear to me this year, it is that OpenCitations is not simply a technical infrastructure. It is a community-driven endeavour whose direction and priorities are shaped by the people and organisations that use, support, and contribute to it, directly or indirectly. The OpenCitations Community Survey, which we launched at the end of 2025 to better understand how our services are being used and where we should focus our future efforts, has received strong participation. We discovered that our community is extraordinarily diverse, including researchers, librarians, institutions, developers, and many others engage with our data in ways we could not have anticipated. Listening to these experiences has helped us better understand where our infrastructure is succeeding, where it still needs improvement, and what kinds of services are most needed today.

This Survey has been the primary channel we have used to enable the community to directly guide OpenCitations' evolution, as our roadmap is now shaped not only by internal technical priorities but primarily by the feedback, expectations, and collaborative proposals emerging from the broader Open Science ecosystem and community. As Director, I see this as one of the greatest strengths of our infrastructure. Building open scholarly infrastructures requires more than technology – it requires participation, trust, and shared responsibility. I would therefore like to thank everyone who contributed ideas, feedback, criticism, time, expertise, and support over the past year. OpenCitations continues to grow because of this collective effort, and our future developments will continue to be shaped together with the community we serve.

OpenCitations' 5 areas of action

OpenCitations' mission is to harvest and openly publish accurate and comprehensive metadata describing the world's academic publications and the scholarly citations that link them, and to preserve persistent access to this information by secure archiving.

To overcome the limitations and achieve its overall objectives, OpenCitations identified five activities to focus on, and is still pursuing the following areas of action in planning its activities yearly:

- **Collect open references from scholarly sources**
- **Expand the number of open citations across the entire scholarly domain**
- **Expand the team**
- **Governance Evolution**
- **Community Building**

Mission

<https://zenodo.org/record/6976670>

Uniqueness

<https://zenodo.org/record/6976696>

Roadmap

<https://trello.com/b/RprHYoKL/open-citations>

Area of Action 1

Collect open references from scholarly sources

Activity 1

During 2025, OpenCitations worked on improving how citation data enters its infrastructure in the first place through collaborations with two external projects, exploring new ways to make the ingestion of citation data more efficient, with the goal of completing ingestion from two new data sources by the end of 2026.

- PKP-Public Knowledge Project, OpenCitations, and TIB-Leibniz-Informationszentrum Technik und Naturwissenschaften und Universitätsbibliothek have begun implementing a workflow in OJS. TIB has developed a plugin for OJS that enables the direct ingestion of OJS citations into OpenCitations. During 2025, OpenCitations also worked on crowdsourcing an automated workflow to ingest these citations directly into its collections

→ <https://github.com/opencitations/crowdsourcing>

- OpenCitations has initiated a collaboration with the Matilda project, a bibliographic and bibliometric platform for open science, focused on validating tabular bibliographic data prior to ingestion, with the aim of including Matilda citations as a future source for OpenCitations:

→ <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00799-025-00425-9>

More generally, the sources managed by OpenCitations during 2025 are:

Crossref

DataCite

NIH-OCC

OpenAIRE

JaLC

Area of Action 2

Expand the number of open citations across the entire scholarly domain

Unique Citations in
OpenCitations Index
(as for December 2025)

2.2 billion

Throughout 2025, the OpenCitations team further refined key steps of its infrastructure redesign, with a strong focus on data refinement and quality improvement.

This effort resulted in the release of **four data dumps** over the year:

- two OpenCitations Meta dumps (February and June), containing bibliographic metadata for all publications included in the OpenCitations Index;
- two OpenCitations Index dumps (March and July), covering citation data and contributing to a total of 2.2 billion citations.

→ <https://download.opencitations.net/>

A major component of the 2025 work was a comprehensive **redesign of the infrastructure architecture**, transitioning toward a microservices-based approach supported by Infrastructure as Code (IaC). This transformation was guided by a long-term vision to enhance scalability and reliability, reduce operational complexity, and ensure that the infrastructure can evolve independently of any single deployment environment. The outcome is a system that can be easily redeployed or transferred with minimal overhead.

→ **Petrella, M. (2025, September 18). OpenCitations and its new IT infrastructure.** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19607220>

HERITRACE, a semantic data curation tool developed for the GLAM sector and introduced at the end of 2024, was tested through a small pilot. The tool distinguishes itself through its ease of use, robust provenance tracking, and high degree of customization. Within OpenCitations, HERITRACE is expected to support users in curating bibliographic and citation metadata, contributing to further improvements in overall data quality:

→ **Massari, A., & Peroni, S. (2025). HERITRACE: A User-Friendly Semantic Data Editor with Change Tracking and Provenance Management for Cultural Heritage Institutions. Umanistica Digitale, 9(20), 317–340.** <https://doi.org/10.6092/issn.2532-8816/21218>

Area of Action 3

Expand the team

During 2025, the OpenCitations development team welcomed 1 new developer, for a total of **12 people** working daily on OpenCitations, including Administrative Officers, Research Fellows and PhD students:

Matteo Guenci

Software Developer - PhD Student

- Support simplifying and enriching the building of citation networks, making data easier to parse, understand and reuse.

Area of Action 4

Governance Evolution

For administrative convenience, OpenCitations is managed by the **Research Centre for Open Scholarly Metadata at the University of Bologna**. Currently, the organizational bodies included in the OpenCitations governance are: the Directors, the International Advisory Board, and the Council. The OpenCitations **"Governance Evolution" working group**, which started in 2022, concluded its activities in 2023, producing a draft governance reform document in collaboration with the legal department of the University of Bologna. In 2024, this draft was further reviewed by a professor of administrative law at the same university, who proposed several reform scenarios compatible with the legal status of OpenCitations.

In 2025, with the support of the dedicated offices of the University of Bologna, this work led to the finalisation of two key documents: the **Rules of Membership and Organisational Structure** and a new **Participation Agreement**, both to be submitted for approval by the OpenCitations Council.

The finalisation of the governance has been approved in early 2026.

During 2025, OpenCitations held **four International Advisory Board Meetings** and an annual Council Meeting.

Area of Action 5

Community Building

In 2025, OpenCitations built on the inputs gathered through the Community Building Working Group of its International Advisory Board (active between 2022 and 2024) to complete a comprehensive rebranding campaign. This process included the launch of a new OpenCitations logo and a fully redesigned website.

In February 2025, the **new logo** was officially announced on OpenCitations' communication channels and blog. This update was not merely aesthetic, but part of a broader effort to better communicate the organisation's core values: openness, transparency, and community. The logo launch coincided with the registration of "OpenCitations" as a trademark with the EUIPO (European Union Intellectual Property Office).

- **Chiara Di Giambattista (February 14, 2025). Announcing the new OpenCitations Logo: a fresh look to reflect our vision. OpenCitations blog. Retrieved May 1, 2026 from <https://doi.org/10.58079/13bgz>**

In July 2025, OpenCitations also launched its new website. The redesign followed the same strategic approach, introducing a cleaner structure and more intuitive navigation to ensure faster access to core services, while also increasing the visibility of OpenCitations as an organisation. The new site places a stronger emphasis on its community-driven nature, with expanded sections dedicated to its mission, values, team, membership programme, partners, and international collaborations. These improvements make it easier for users to engage with and understand OpenCitations' work.

As part of the rebranding effort, the website also includes a dedicated page outlining the OpenCitations brand identity and guidelines for logo usage.

- **Chiara Di Giambattista (July 1, 2025). Welcome to the new OpenCitations website! OpenCitations blog. Retrieved April 30, 2026 from <https://doi.org/10.58079/148p7>**

Additionally, the new website enabled the integration of a subscription form for the OpenCitations newsletter, launched in November 2025. This new communication channel provides subscribers with periodic updates on both technical developments and community activities.

The new logo of OpenCitations, as a combination of four different elements: letter O; letter C; an eye and the citation markups

Community Survey

Between October and December 2025, OpenCitations conducted a [Community Survey](#), as part of its ongoing commitment to remain a community-driven and community-governed infrastructure.

The survey was developed with the support of the International Advisory Board and widely circulated across the academic community, targeting a broad audience that included users, member institutions, partners, and individuals new to OpenCitations. The survey covered both technical and outreach dimensions to gather structured feedback on how OpenCitations is perceived, used, and expected to evolve within an increasingly complex open citation ecosystem.

By directly consulting its community, OpenCitations aimed to ensure that its future priorities align with the evolving needs of the scholarly landscape. The insights collected through this process are informing the 2026 roadmap.

→ **Chiara Di Giambattista (October 22, 2025). Shape the future of OpenCitations: take our Community Survey. OpenCitations blog. Retrieved May 1, 2026 from <https://doi.org/10.58079/150dc>**

OpenCitations Blog

The [OpenCitations blog](#) is hosted on the academic blogs platform Hypotheses.org, and the blog feed is featured on Rogue Scholar, an archive of science blogs aiming to index full-text of blog posts, establish a full-text search, and register DOIs and metadata for all posts. In 2025, we published [six blog posts](#). Compared to the previous years, the blog experienced a growth in website traffic.

Among those, the most viewed blog post was the following:

→ **Chiara Di Giambattista (January 30, 2025). Wheels Are in Motion: OpenCitations' progress in 2024. OpenCitations blog. Retrieved May 4, 2026 from <https://doi.org/10.58079/137ne>**

Social Media Management

Social media platforms (X, Mastodon, LinkedIn, Bluesky) were used to share and promote blog content, event participation, and major technical developments.

We discontinued posting on Threads, where engagement was nonexistent. We also reduced interactions on X, with the perspective of a possible pause in posting, to focus on LinkedIn, Mastodon, and Bluesky.

Communication Partnerships

A wide range of networks and projects contributed to disseminating OpenCitations news, establishing a mutually beneficial exchange of communication and outreach activities. Among these, we highlight the following:

- **OpenAIRE** cross-posted OpenCitations news on social media, particularly in relation to the Community Survey.
- **The Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information** promoted the Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 through a dedicated page on its website and by amplifying OpenCitations communications on social media. It also supported the dissemination of the Community Survey via a dedicated community mailing list.
- **SCOSS** reposted OpenCitations updates on social media. OpenCitations participated in the SCOSS Family Communication Group, which focuses on strategic reflection and practical support to strengthen communication and dissemination across open infrastructures.
- The **GraspOS** communication team promoted the Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 in its newsletter, along with other relevant updates from OpenCitations.
- The **GRAPHIA** and **LUMEN** projects helped disseminate information about the Community Survey through their newsletters, while OpenCitations reciprocally promoted these projects on social media channels.

Participation in events and conferences

During 2025, OpenCitations participated in numerous events and conferences that helped reach out to a wider community.

20 February 2025

OASPA Webinar on Practical Applications of Open Infrastructure Tools for Scholarly Communication (online)

Invited talk of Silvio Peroni (Director) in the context of the online event "Practical Applications of Open Infrastructure Tools for Scholarly Communication", organized by OASPA.

- Peroni, S. (2025, February 20). OpenCitations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14901157>

29 May 2025

Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (Bologna, Italy)

Keynote speech by OpenCitations at the Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata (WOOC 2025), held in Bologna on 28–29 May 2025 and organized by the University of Bologna, OpenCitations and the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information.

- Di Giambattista, C., & Heibi, I. (2025, October). OpenCitations: an open infrastructure enabling Open Research Information. Workshop on Open Citations & Open Scholarly Metadata 2025 (WOOC-2025), Bologna, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17199853>

2 July 2025

Informazioni aperte sulla ricerca: fonti e implementazioni (Milan, Italy)

Talk "How to use OpenCitations data: formats, dumps, APIs" by Silvio Peroni and Ivan Heibi (CTO), given in the context of the event "Informazioni aperte sulla ricerca: fonti e implementazioni".

- Peroni, S., & Heibi, I. (2025, July 2). How to use OpenCitations data: formats, dumps, APIs. Informazioni aperte sulla ricerca: fonti e implementazioni, Milan, Italy. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15796741>

9 July 2025

Training seminar of the CoARA Italian National Chapter "Risorse aperte per il monitoraggio e la valutazione della ricerca" (online)

The seminar, organized as part of the outreach and training activities of the Italian National Chapter of COARA, focused on the use of open data and open infrastructures for research assessment. During the event, Silvio Peroni presented OpenCitations as a key infrastructure supporting transparency and openness in bibliographic data.

- Peroni, S. (2025, July 9). OpenCitations, un'infrastruttura di Scienza Aperta dedicata alla pubblicazione di informazioni bibliografiche e citazionali. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15846868>

10 September 2025

csv.conf,v9 (Bologna, Italy)

1. Presentation by Silvio Peroni held in the csv.conf,v9 conference, about OpenCitations and the milestones that enabled the creation of the concept of open citations and all the related Open Science infrastructures providing this particular kind of open research information.

- Peroni, S. (2025, September 10). How did we get to OpenCitations: a brief history of open scholarly citations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17093870>

2. Presentation by Arcangelo Massari: Mapping the unmapped citation landscape: how crowdsourcing will fill the citation gap

- Massari, A. (2025, September 11). Mapping the unmapped citation landscape: how crowdsourcing will fill the citation gap. csv.conf,v9, Bologna. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17098600>

15 September 2025

FICLIT White Night (Bologna, Italy)

On September 15, OpenCitations took part in the White Night of the FICLIT Department (Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna), as part of the Research Centre for Open Scholarly Metadata.

Photos available at <https://ficlit.unibo.it/it/con-societa-e-impresa/presentazione/notte-bianca-ficlit-2025>

18 September 2025

Dagstuhl Seminar 25381: Open Scholarly Information Systems: Status Quo, Challenges, Opportunities (Dagstuhl, Germany)

Presentation by Mario Petrella (SysAdmin, OpenCitations), presented in the context of "Dagstuhl Seminar 25381 Open Scholarly Information Systems: Status Quo, Challenges, Opportunities" (Sept.14-19).

- Petrella, M. (2025, September 18). OpenCitations and its new IT infrastructure. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19607220>

30 September 2025

Working Group "Sustaining Infrastructures - Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information (online)

Talk by Chiara Di Giambattista (Communications Director at OpenCitations) on the OpenCitations sustainability model, delivered within Working Group 5 "Sustaining Infrastructures" of the Barcelona Declaration on Open research Information together with Claudio Fabbri (Research Manager).

- Di Giambattista, C., & Fabbri, C. (2025, September 30). OpenCitations' steps towards sustainability. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17244180>

22 October 2025

Open and Engaged 2025 (online)

Talk "The path to open: premises and achievements after more than a decade of OpenCitations" by Silvio Peroni given during the event [Open and Engaged 2025](#), held online and organised by the British Library.

- Peroni, S. (2025, October 22). The path to open: premises and achievements after more than a decade of OpenCitations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17417193>

11-12 November 2025

GraspOS Final Conference (Pisa, Italy)

Poster by OpenCitations presented in the context of the GraspOS Final Conference (Pisa, 11-12 November 2025).

- Peroni, S., & Di Giambattista, C. (2025). OpenCitations for Research Assessment. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17543818>

13 November 2025

Tavola rotonda: La prospettiva della Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information (Pisa, Italy)

Presentation held during the round table within the conference "[Per una nuova cultura della valutazione della ricerca: la riforma di CoARA in Italia - Due anni di Capitolo Nazionale Italiano](#)", held in Pisa, Italy.

- Peroni, S. (2025, November 13). Tavola rotonda: La prospettiva della Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information (DORI). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17607506>

11 December 2025

SCOSS Showcase webinar (online)

Pitch presentation of OpenCitations in the webinar organized by the Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS), an event featuring 18 open infrastructures worldwide.

- Report, slides and recording available at <https://scoss.org/what-collective-funding-makes-possible-highlights-from-the-2025-scoss-showcase/>

19 December 2025

SESAME Workshop 2025 (online)

Online talk "An overview of OpenCitations, an open infrastructure to transform research assessment practices" given by Silvio Peroni in the [SESAME Workshop 2025](#).

- Peroni, S. (2025, December 19). OpenCitations: recent developments and future directions. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17991410>

Events hosted by OpenCitations

Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata 2025

Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna and OpenCitations hosted the Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata (WOOC) in Bologna on May 28–29, 2025, co-organized with the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information. Over two days, researchers, publishers, funders, policy-makers, and infrastructure providers came together to discuss open access to research information. The first day was dedicated to the Bologna Meeting on Open Research Information, while the second focused on community presentations, posters, and invited talks, creating a space where policy, infrastructure, and scholarly practice could converge. The proceedings of invited and selected talks and posters are available on Zenodo, providing open access to the contributions shared during the workshop.

- Heibi, I., Di Giambattista, C., & Peroni, S. (2025, October). Proceedings of the Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata (WOOC 2025) – Index Volume. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17199918>

GraspOS Third Plenary Meeting

The third in-presence meeting of the consortium was hosted by the University of Bologna and OpenCitations soon after the Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata, on May 30th, providing an opportunity for strategic planning, in-depth discussion of project outcomes, and team building.

OpenCitations Annual Webinar and Council Meeting

On December 10, OpenCitations held the OpenCitations Annual Webinar for the OpenCitations Council members, an internal event during which the OpenCitations director provided an overview of OpenCitations and presented the latest updates and future developments.

- Peroni, S. (2025, December 10). OpenCitations Annual Webinar 2025. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17939974>

Project partnerships, funded applications and R&D projects

LUMEN (2025-2027)

The LUMEN project is an initiative to advance cross-domain collaboration and discovery processes in four academic fields: Mathematics (Maths), Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), Earth System Science (ES) and Molecular Dynamics (MD). Through interdisciplinary solutions spanning all four domains, LUMEN sets out to significantly improve discovery by innovation, simplifying initial research phases and facilitating access to advanced AI-powered tools for researchers. LUMEN aims to transform and strengthen EOSC services by promoting innovative and customisable solutions for data discovery.

Within this framework, OpenCitations contributes to the Metrics Service by providing open citation data that enables transparent and reproducible impact indicators for publications and author profiles. Building on the OPERAS Metrics service, the integration of OpenCitations data supports the development of responsible metrics aligned with the principles of CoARA.

GRAPHIA (2025-2027)

The GRAPHIA project started on January 1st, 2025, with the aim of creating the first comprehensive Social Science and Humanities (SSH) Knowledge Graph designed to integrate fragmented data into a unified entry point. Part of OpenCitations' personnel working at the University of Bologna is involved in GRAPHIA for the development of tools to enable data extraction from PDFs, and OpenCitations itself serves in the project as a source of information for the Knowledge Graph.

GraspOS (2023-2025)

The GraspOS project, launched on January 1, 2023, set out to create an open and trusted federated infrastructure for next-generation research metrics and indicators. Its objective was to build and operate a data infrastructure to support policy reforms and pave the way toward a responsible research assessment system that embeds Open Science (OS) practices and accelerates their adoption across Europe. Within GraspOS, OpenCitations contributed as one of the Data Asset Sources, providing both raw and structured citation data to support OS-aware research assessment processes and the calculation of indicators and evidence. Researchers from OpenCitations and the University of Bologna developed a tool for extracting citation data from PDFs, enriched with additional information on citation intent (e.g., reuse of methods, agreement with claims) through machine-learning techniques. Throughout the project, OpenCitations also collaborated closely with partners such as OpenAIRE.

In 2025, members of the consortium participated in the Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata 2025, followed by the third Plenary Meeting held in Bologna, which provided an opportunity to consolidate results and align future perspectives. The GraspOS Final Conference, held in Pisa in November, marked the conclusion of the project and offered a key moment to reflect on its achievements and overall impact.

- Provost, L., & Malaguarnera, G. (2025). GraspOS Deliverable: Final Brief Report (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18084673>

SCOSS Family

After participating in the second funding cycle of the SCOSS program (2019–2023), OpenCitations is now part of the SCOSS Family, a community of practice bringing together infrastructures from all SCOSS pledging rounds. This involves active participation in internal working groups aimed at sharing resources, fostering collaboration, and strengthening impact within the open science ecosystem.

During 2025, we contributed to discussions to enhance and showcase the interconnections and relationships among infrastructures. An interactive graphical visualisation of these relationships, covering both technical integrations and collaborative links, is available here: <https://scoss.org/what-is-scoss/scossfamily/#exp>

Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information

OpenCitations is one of the supporters of the [Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information](#), a key initiative launched in April 2024 aimed at fostering open access to scholarly information and advancing the principles of open science. This aligns closely with OpenCitations' mission to promote transparency, accessibility, and collaboration in scholarly communication.

In 2025, OpenCitations collaborated closely with the Barcelona Declaration to organise the Bologna Meeting on Open Research Information. In addition, members of the OpenCitations team joined three [working groups](#) promoted by the Declaration (Sustaining Infrastructures, Evidence of Benefits of Open Research Information, and Replacing Closed Systems for Research Information) actively contributing to advancing open, community-driven alternatives to proprietary research information systems.

Catalogues and Collections

OpenCitations is currently included in the Invest in Open Infrastructure's tool [InfraFinder](#), in the [OpenAIRE Service Catalogue](#), in EOSC through the [EOSC Italian Node](#) and in the [JISC Collections](#).

An overview of OpenCitations' R&D projects, partnerships and networks across the years

Financial report

Expenditure for the year 2025:

Salaries for three computer specialists, one Policy Advocate and Community Outreach Officer, and the OpenCitations Manager / Accountant / Administrator	116.899,70
Costs of conference attendance/missions and travels	5.133,93
Crossref subscriptions	691,50
Hardware	168,36
Web services and tools	828,40
Services for events	42,70
Total	123.764,59€

Income for the year 2025:

Funder Name	Country
Berner Fachhochschule	Switzerland
Brock University	Canada
CERN	Switzerland
Dutch Research Council	The Netherlands
École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne	Switzerland
Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zürich	Switzerland
Eurasia Academic Publishing Group	Honk Kong; The Netherlands
European University Institute	Italy
French Open Science Committee	France
Ghent University	Belgium
Institut de Radioprotection et de Sûreté Nucléaire	France
Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer	France
Institut Pasteur	France
Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	Belgium
McMaster University	Canada

Royal Danish Library	Denmark
Sorbonne Université	France
Spanish National Research Council	Spain
Tampere University including Tampere University Hospital	Finland
Universität Bern	Switzerland
Universität St Gallen	Switzerland
Universität Zürich	Switzerland
Universitäts- und Landesbibliothek Darmstadt	Germany
Université de Fribourg	Switzerland
Université de Lorraine	France
Université de Montréal	Canada
Université de Neuchâtel	Switzerland
Université de Rennes	France
Université de Rennes II Haute-Bretagne	France
Université Jean Monnet Saint-Etienne	France
Université Paris Nanterre	France
Université Paris-Saclay	France
University of Alberta	Canada
University of Helsinki including Helsinki University Central Hospital	Finland
University of Ottawa	Canada
University of Toronto	Canada
Zürcher Hochschule der Künste	Switzerland
Total revenues for 2025	241.250,00€

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Social Media

Bluesky: <https://bsky.app/profile/opencitations.bsky.social>

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/opencitations/>

Mastodon: <https://scicomm.xyz/@opencitations>

X: <http://www.twitter.com/opencitations>

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SIGNATURE

